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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY 56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadinovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES..... 84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	
ORGANIZATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN NON-STATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS .	148
Xojiboyev Muxiddin Shodimuxamedovich	
THE NATURE AND ESSENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES IN MASS MEDIA ORGANIZATIONS.....	151
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ALGORITHMS FOR RECOVERING MISSING (NAN) VALUES IN INFORMATION SYSTEM DATA	156
Yarmatov Sherzodjon Shokir oglu, Orifov Oxunjon Fazliddinzoda	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES	167
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
IMPROVING LOAN PORTFOLIO QUALITY AND CREDIT RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS	173
Turgunov Nodirbek Muminjanovich	
INNOVATION CAPABILITIES AND EXPORT PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF SUPPLY CHAIN INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION — EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	177
Mukhammadyaminova Shakhzoda	
URBAN PLANNING OF TRANSPORT INTERCHANGE HUBS NEAR TUBERCULOSIS CARE FACILITIES IN UZBEKISTAN	183
Gabibova Irina Vagifovna, Abdumuminova Diyora Gayratovna	
ADAPTING INTERNAL AUDIT STANDARDS IN BUDGET ORGANIZATIONS TO PUBLIC PROCUREMENT PRACTICES.....	192
Meliboyev Askar Eshmuratovich	
ECONOMETRIC EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN KHOREZM REGION	197
Otajanov Umid Abdullayevich	
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF MODERN RECLAMATION AND GIS TECHNOLOGIES ON SALINE SOILS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN.....	205
Tajibaev Berdakh	
ISSUES REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE “TOLLING OPERATIONS” MODULE IN THE GOODS MOVEMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM UNDER THE CUSTOMS TERRITORY PROCESSING REGIME	212
Lutpullaev Shukrullo Kudratullaevich	

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN ENHANCING TOURISM-RELATED BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN	218
Akmaljon Odilov	
INTERNATIONAL TRENDS OF DIGITALIZATION IN CUSTOMS MANAGEMENT	222
Radjapova Latofat Sardarovna	
THE ROLE OF TAX POLICY IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY	230
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi	
PRACTICES IN ENTERPRISE COST STRUCTURE MANAGEMENT AND DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT	236
Aymukhammedova Amina Kakajanovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	242
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
RECONCEPTUALIZING BUSINESS INCUBATORS IN STARTUP ECOSYSTEMS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS	246
Gafujon Usmanov	
DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN MARKETING APPROACHES TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES	257
Safarov Bakhtiyor Djurakulovich	
MECHANISMS FOR EVALUATING AND IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN THE PUBLIC TRANSPORT SECTOR	263
Berdiyorov Temur Azamatovich	
THE INFLUENCE OF HYDRODYNAMIC ASPECTS OF GROUNDWATER LEVEL RISE ON URBAN WATERLOGGING	268
B.D. Abdullaev, B.R. Nasibov, Sh.T. Irgashev, D. Abdullaev	
BASIC INFORMATION MODEL OF A DIGITAL OBJECT	277
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich, Karakhanova Alsu Muratalievna, Keldiyorov Sirojiddin Tura ugli, Zayniddinova Zebiniso Akmalovna	
COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE AND TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SOLAR PANEL MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS	281
Urishev Omadjon, Kushakova Sarvinoz, Kamolboyev Sirojbek	
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR FORMING ECOLOGICALLY ORIENTED MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	294
Kholov Hamza Tajiddinovich	
INVESTIGATION OF GERMANIUM EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY FROM TECHNOGENIC METALLURGICAL WASTE	301
Yormatov Dostonbek, Shodiyev Abbos, Muhammadiyev Elbek	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING RESOURCE EFFICIENCY AND OPTIMIZING PRODUCTION COSTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY	309
Utbasarov Doniyorjon Bakhtiyarovich	
THEORETICAL, PRACTICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF AUDITING THE ACTIVITIES OF ECONOMIC ENTITIES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS	318
Mirzaeva Sabina Khushnudovna, Khaydarova Dildora Djakhongirovna	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON WOMEN'S LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF UZBEKISTAN UNDER INDUSTRY 4.0	322
Doniyorova Zukhrabonu Alisher qizi	
LEVEL OF ENSURING FOOD SECURITY: IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS AND INSTRUMENTS	328
Sodiqjon Qodirovich Mattiyev	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY, AND LOCALIZATION POLICY OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT SYSTEM	334
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASH VOSITASIDA	339
Bozorova Madina Raxmat qizi	

PROJECT-ORIENTED ESP32 IOT CURRICULUM WITH A SHARED-RESOURCE LABORATORY MODEL: DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, AND LESSONS LEARNED	344
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Lazizbek Yusupov	
FIVE-CRITERION METHODOLOGY OF INTERNAL CONTROL ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	353
Babakulova Matluba Kurbannazarovna	
THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION–INDUSTRY INTEGRATION IN THE CONTEXT OF THE KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY.....	357
Uzaydullayev Sherzod Shukurullayevich	
MECHANISMS AND DIRECTIONS FOR DEEPENING REGIONAL INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	361
Akbarova Kamola Akmaljonovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN HEALTHCARE INSTITUTIONS	368
Saidov Suhrob Shodmonovich	
IMPROVING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN’S SERVICE SECTOR: BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS.....	371
Shermatov Axror Abdixakimovich	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING CUSTOMS RISK PROFILE INDICATORS BASED ON MATHEMATICAL AND STATISTICAL METHODS	377
Niyazov Sherzod Shovkat ugli	
AN INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK FOR CRYPTO-ASSET REGULATION: ADDRESSING LEGAL UNCERTAINTY IN DIGITAL FINANCIAL SYSTEMS	385
Iminokhunov Abdukokhor A., Khakimov Abdurakhmon Mukhammad-Ali ugli	
THEORETICAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE SERVICE SECTOR	396
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
REGIONAL ASSESSMENT OF THE OPENNESS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON A SYNTHETIC INDICATOR.....	401
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE REGIONAL INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT ASSESSMENT CRITERIA AND INDICATORS SYSTEM.....	407
Maxmudov Jasurbek Ergashevich	
ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT ATTRACTION PRACTICES IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	412
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli	
ASSESSMENT OF SOURCES OF EQUITY FORMATION IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THEIR USE.....	421
Savinova Galina Anatolevna	
DIGITAL MARKETING INTEGRATION, KPI ARCHITECTURE AND CAUSAL EVALUATION OF ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS IN EMERGING MARKETS: A CONCEPTUAL-METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR UZBEKISTAN	429
Bakhtiyor Ruziev Eshmuminovich	
IMPROVING FOREIGN EXCHANGE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN	434
B.K. Tugalov	
CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL DIVERSITY OF HOOFED ANIMALS IN THE TUGAI FORESTS OF THE SOUTHERN ARAL REGION UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS.....	438
J. U. Tilepov, A. A. Jumamuratova	
ECONOMETRIC ASSESSMENT MECHANISMS OF THE IMPACT OF TRADE SERVICE QUALITY INDICATORS ON THE LEVEL OF COMPETITIVENESS	442
Toxirov Javlon Raximovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA BIZNES MUHITINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING AHAMIYATI ..	447
Xazratov Abror Panjiyevich, Muratkulov Xumoyun Dilshodovich	

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COTTON PROCESSING INDUSTRY IN BUSINESS ENTITIES	452
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li, Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzayevich	
BALANCING ECONOMIC GROWTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN TOURISM.....	456
Kamalova Malika Umidjanovna, Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR IMPROVING FACE-ID TECHNOLOGY IN ENSURING INFORMATION SECURITY ON E-PLATFORMS.....	462
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
SOLIQLAR VA DAVLAT BUDJETI: SOLIQ TIZIMINING BUDJETIGA TA'SIRI.....	467
Izbosarov Bobur Baxriddinovich, Umirov Sherzod Baxriddinovich	
СИСТЕМНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ БАНКОВСКОГО СЕКТОРА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	472
Аширкулов Диорбек Алишер угли, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовевна	
THE IMPACT OF INFLATION ON THE ECONOMY AND WAYS TO REDUCE IT	479
Abdullaeva Zulfiya Izzatovna, Ashurova Jasmina Jora qizi	
КОЛЛИЗИИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО И СЕМЕЙНОГО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВА В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СУПРУГОВ.....	483
Рашидова Зилола Жавлонбековна	
SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES (SME) AND DISTRICT-LEVEL PANEL DATA ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	487
Ismoilov Elyorjon Makhamadali ugli, Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ONLINE PLATFORMS IN THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	495
Bakayev Ziyovuddinxon Toshbolta o'g'li	
CHINA'S DIGITAL YUAN (E-CNY) PROJECT: ANALYSIS OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT, PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE, AND POSSIBILITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN.....	500
Tashquziyev Suxrob Abdurazzak ugli	
VALYUTA KURSI REJIMLARI (ERKIN SUZUVCHI, BOG'LANGAN, ARALASH): MILLIY VALYUTA BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRINI NAZARIY SOLISHTIRISH.....	505
G'afurov Olimjon G'olib o'g'li	
IMPACT OF DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN, STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND TRENDS	510
Ibodullayev Navro'zbek Ikram o'g'li, Akbarov Nodir G'ofurovich	
THE IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE-ORIENTED FISCAL POLICY ON REGIONAL COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Ne'matov Ne'matulla Erkinboyevich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA ICHKI AUDIT METODOLOGIYASI: XALQARO STANDARTLAR VA MILLIY AMALIYOTNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	523
Saitmuratov Saitmuarat Masharip o'g'li	
AHOLINING BANKLARDAGI OMONATLARINI KAFOLATLASH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	528
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
ISSUES IN DETERMINING THE MATERIALITY LEVEL IN AUDIT FIRMS.....	536
Pirnazarova Juldiz Djamiljan qizi	

ISSUES IN DETERMINING THE MATERIALITY LEVEL IN AUDIT FIRMS

Pirnazarova Juldiz Djamiljan qizi

Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh,

Assistent of the «Accounting and Auditing» department

E-mail: yulduzpirnazarova55@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0000-1217-5682

Abstract. This article provides an empirical analysis of the importance of identifying and assessing risk indicators and materiality levels in organizing risk-based audits. The article also examines the criteria for determining materiality, its quantitative and qualitative aspects, as well as the procedure for applying materiality at various stages of the audit. It is substantiated that regular reassessment of the materiality level contributes to improving audit efficiency and reducing audit risk.

Keywords: materiality, audit, risk, audit organizations, ISA 320, assets, profit, revenue.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada riskka asoslangan auditni tashkil etishda xavf ko'rsatkichlari va muhimlik darajasini aniqlash hamda baholashning ahamiyati empirik jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, maqolada muhimlikni aniqlash mezonlari, uning miqdoriy va sifat jihatlari hamda auditning turli bosqichlarida qo'llash tartibi yoritilgan. Muhimlik darajasini muntazam ravishda qayta baholab borish audit samaradorligini oshirish va auditorlik riskini kamaytirishga xizmat qilishi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: muhimlik, audit, risk, auditorlik tashkilotlari, XAS 320, aktivlar, foyda, tushum.

Аннотация. В данной статье проведён эмпирический анализ значения определения и оценки показателей риска, а также уровня существенности при организации риск-ориентированного аудита. Также рассмотрены критерии определения существенности, её количественные и качественные аспекты, а также порядок применения на различных этапах аудита. Обосновано, что регулярная переоценка уровня существенности способствует повышению эффективности аудита и снижению аудиторского риска.

Ключевые слова: существенность, аудит, риск, аудиторские организации, MCA 320, активы, прибыль, выручка.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of recent reforms in the field of auditing in Uzbekistan, a number of regulatory documents have been adopted, which have had a significant impact on the development of the sector. In particular, the transition to International Standards on Auditing in Uzbekistan is being implemented in accordance with Resolution No. PQ-3946 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 19, 2018, "On Measures for the Further Development of Auditing Activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan"¹. Based on this resolution, fundamental reforms have been introduced in the national audit services sector. In this regard, in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-677 dated February 25, 2021, "On Auditing Activities"², audit organizations have begun conducting their activities on the basis of International Standards on Auditing.

Since the concept of materiality, which is applied throughout the entire audit process by audit organizations, is a matter of professional judgment, different approaches exist regarding its practical application. Although certain common features are observed in the application of this concept in international practice, there remain opportunities to further improve methodological approaches to its application in national audit practice.

To assess the quality of ongoing changes in the field of auditing, particularly the application of International Standards on Auditing in audit practice, it is possible to obtain relevant information on qualitative developments by conducting questionnaire surveys among practicing auditors.

Monographic studies show that the materiality level is influenced by the degree of reliance placed on the client's internal control system, the needs of stakeholders, the auditor's professional experience, the size of the client company, and the likelihood that an identified error may have legal implications. Among these factors,

1 O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining O'zbekiston Respublikasida «Auditorlik faoliyatini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida» qarori, 19.09.2018 yildagi PQ-3946-son <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-3914502>

2 O'zbekiston Respublikasining «Auditorlik faoliyati to'g'risida» qonuni, 25.02.2021 yildagi O'RQ-677-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-5307886>

increased confidence in the internal control system allows for the determination of a higher materiality level by reducing the likelihood of errors or fraud. An increase in the size of the audited entity generally leads to a decrease in the materiality percentage applied. The auditor's professional experience, particularly in applying professional judgment, also affects the determination of the materiality level. In addition, along with the auditor's experience, the nature of the relationship between the client and the audit firm may also influence the determination of materiality.

Furthermore, it is noted that the likelihood of an identified error having legal implications may also affect the materiality level. When the consequences of such an error are expected to be significant, an increase in the probability of legal implications may lead to a lower materiality level.

In the area under study, in order to answer the question of whether the materiality level is determined uniformly in national audit practice, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: There is no correlation between the size of the audited company and the established materiality level.

H2: There is no relationship between the degree of closeness to the client and the determined materiality level.

H3: The auditor's professional experience does not affect the materiality level.

H4: There is no relationship between confidence in the internal control system and the determined materiality level.

H5: There is no relationship between the likelihood of an error having legal implications and the materiality level.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In Uzbekistan, many economists have expressed their scholarly views on the concept of materiality in auditing.

In particular, the theoretical, organizational, and methodological aspects of determining the level of materiality in auditing have been studied in the research works of B. Bolibekov, R. D. Dusmuratov, Sh. Ilkhamov, N. F. Karimov, Z. T. Mamatov, R. Tairov, K. U. Urazov, B. A. Khasanova, M. M. Tulakhodjaeva, D. Shaulova, E. A. Prokudin, N. T. Khasanova, and other scholars.

According to Professor R. D. Dusmuratov, "the concept of materiality is the primary and fundamental basis for determining the possible amount of audit error, the scope of the audit procedures to be performed, and the form of the auditor's report, whether positive or negative." In this definition, the concept of "materiality" is interpreted through the notion of "significance." The author emphasizes that the materiality indicator ultimately serves as a basis for determining both the scope of the audit and the form of the auditor's report.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Among empirical methods, a Likert scale questionnaire was used to analyze the application of ISA 320, "Materiality in Planning and Performing an Audit," by auditors and to identify the factors influencing its practical implementation. This method also makes it possible to determine which factors are considered when establishing the materiality level. The Likert scale is a widely used research method that enables the qualitative assessment of changes and perceptions in the field.

The questionnaire developed within the framework of this study consists of two sections. The first section is aimed at identifying the demographic characteristics of the respondents, while the second section focuses on examining the factors that influence the process of determining the materiality level. The responses to the questionnaire were analyzed, and relevant findings were formulated based on the scientific conclusions obtained. Issues related to determining materiality in the planning and performance of a mandatory audit, the existing scientific literature, and the requirements of ISA 320 were used as the methodological basis of the study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data collected from the respondents' answers were analyzed using frequency analysis and weighted average values. Based on the information obtained regarding the concept of materiality and the factors influencing the determination of the materiality level in audit practice, the views of auditors operating in the field were examined, and relevant scientific interpretations were developed within the framework of these findings.

As part of the practical section of the study, questionnaire responses were obtained from 115 independent auditors operating in Uzbekistan (Table 1).

Table 1

How much do you care about which indicator to take when deciding on importance? Mark the answers on a scale from 1 to 5! (I get 1 the least in my answers, 2, 3, 4, 5 the most)³

Indicators	1	Priority level (1 highest, 5 lowest)					Total	Average Formula (1)
		2	3	4	5	x_i		
Total assets	Number (n)	20	10	15	20	50	115	3,61
	%	17,4	8,7	13,0	17,4	43,5	100	
Income	Number (n)	20,0	20,0	45,0	80,0	250,0	415,0	4,09
	%	10	10	5	25	65	115	
Retained earnings	Number (n)	8,7	8,7	4,3	21,7	56,5	100	2,83
	%	10,0	20,0	15,0	100,0	325,0	470,0	
Profit before tax	Number (n)	10	30	55	10	10	115	3,65
	%	8,7	26,1	47,8	8,7	8,7	100	
Net profit	Number (n)	10,0	60,0	165,0	40,0	50,0	325,0	3,52
	%	10	10	30	25	40	115	
Gross profit	Number (n)	8,7	8,7	26,1	21,7	34,8	100	3,17
	%	10,0	20,0	90,0	100,0	200,0	420,0	
Charter capital	Number (n)	10	15	35	15	40	115	2,83
	%	8,7	13,0	30,4	13,0	34,8	100	
	Number (n)	10,0	30,0	105,0	60,0	200,0	405,0	
	%	15	15	40	25	20	115	
	Number (n)	13,0	13,0	34,8	21,7	17,4	100	
	%	15,0	30,0	120,0	100,0	100,0	365,0	
	Number (n)	20	30	20	40	5	115	
	%	17,4	26,1	17,4	34,8	4,3	100	
	Number (n)	20,0	60,0	60,0	160,0	25,0	325,0	
	%							

Auditors participating in the questionnaire were asked to answer the question, “How important is each indicator when determining materiality?” on a scale from 1 to 5 according to its level of significance. To analyze the responses and determine the importance of each indicator, total assets, revenue, retained earnings, profit before tax, net profit, gross profit, and authorized capital were considered as the main indicators.

In analyzing the responses of the auditor-respondents, the weighted average value was determined for each indicator. The weighted average value was calculated using Formula 1.

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 X_i * n}{N} \quad (\text{formula 1})^4$$

Here, x represents values from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates the lowest level of significance and 5 indicates the highest level. The variable n denotes the number of respondents who selected a particular answer, while N represents the total number of respondents.

The analysis of the responses to this question showed that auditors most frequently select revenue as the primary benchmark when determining materiality. Among the weighted average values, revenue had the highest score, with 4.09 out of 5. The next most commonly selected benchmark was profit before tax, which scored 3.65 on the 5-point scale. The total assets indicator scored 3.61 out of 5, while the net profit indicator was rated at 3.52.

Among the analyzed indicators, retained earnings and authorized capital received comparatively lower scores. Each of these indicators was assigned 2.83 points.

3 author’s development
4 Author’s development

Based on the analysis conducted, it can be stated that in more than 80% of cases, practicing auditors primarily use revenue as the benchmark for determining materiality in audits. It was also found that profit before tax is used as the base indicator for determining materiality in up to 80% of cases, while total assets and net profit indicators are used in approximately 70% of cases. The likelihood of selecting the remaining indicators was below 70% (Table 2).

Table 2
Factors influencing the determination of the significance indicator⁵

Factors	Quantity	%
Audit company's audit policy	20	17.39
The auditor's applied constant indicator/percentage	20	17.39
Case specific to the client under review	70	60.87
Other	5	4.35
Total	115	100.00

When auditors participating in the questionnaire were asked about the factors influencing the determination of the materiality level, 60.87% of them stated that the specific circumstances of the client under audit influence the determination of materiality. In addition, 17.39% of auditors indicated that the audit firm's review policy and the fixed indicator or percentage applied by the auditor also affect this process.

Based on the responses to this question, it can be concluded that, when determining materiality, auditors pay greater attention to client-specific aspects. This approach is fully justified in audit practice, since although materiality is expressed as a numerical value, it is also important to consider factors specific to the client when establishing the materiality level⁶. Most studies emphasize that, in determining materiality, attention should also be paid to both external and internal qualitative factors affecting the client's activities⁷. Therefore, it can be said that in national auditing practice, a reasonably correct approach, at least in theory, has been established for determining the materiality level (Table 3).

Table 3
Which customer parameters do you consider when determining the importance indicator?⁸

No	Options	Priority level					Total	Moderately
		1.	2.	3.	4.	5.		
1.	Client's financial standing	20	20	25	15	35	115	3.22
		17.4	17.4	21.7	13.0	30.4	100.0	
		20	40	75	60	175	370	
2.	Purposes of the enterprise / shareholders (owners)	20	10	30	20	35	115	3.35
		17.4	8.7	26.1	17.4	30.4	100.0	
		20	20	90	80	175	385	
3.	The auditor's relationship with shareholders	50	5	20	25	15	115	2.57
		43.5	4.3	17.4	21.7	13.0	100.0	
		50	10	60	100	75	295	
4.	Level of confidence in the internal control system	25	15	10	25	40	115	3.35
		21.7	13.0	8.7	21.7	34.8	100.0	
		25	30	30	100	200	385	

5 author's development

6 Popa, I. E., Span, G., Dumitru, M., Dumitru, V. F., & Filip, C. L. (2013). Empirical Study on the Implications of Qualitative Factors in Making Decisions Related to the Materiality Level: The Case of Romania. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 26 (4), 43–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677x.2013.11517629>

7 Masiulevičius, A., & Lakis, V. (2022). Application of Qualitative Characteristics to Evaluate Misstatements in Financial Statements: Evidence from Factual Audit Data. *Ekonomika*, 101 (2), 6–21. <https://doi.org/10.15388/ekon.2022.101.2.1>

8 author's development

5.	Needs of Financial Information Users	25	15	15	20	40	115	3.30
		21.7	13.0	13.0	17.4	34.8	100.0	
6.	Work experience and qualifications of the auditor	25	30	45	80	200	380	3.26
		25	5.	35	15	35	115	
		21.7	4.3	30.4	13.0	30.4	100.0	
7.	General state of the industry in which the enterprise operates	25	10	105	60	175	375	3.22
		25	15	20	20	35	115	
		21.7	13.0	17.4	17.4	30.4	100.0	
8.	Auditor's attitude towards risk	25	30	60	80	175	370	3.48
		15	20	25	5	50	115	
		13.0	17.4	21.7	4.3	43.5	100.0	
9.	The scale (size) of the client enterprise	15	40	75	20	250	400	3.39
		15	25	15	20	40	115	
		13.0	21.7	13.0	17.4	34.8	100.0	
10.	Customer Leadership Goals	15	50	45	80	200	390	3.26
		10	20	40	20	25	115	
		8.7	17.4	34.8	17.4	21.7	100.0	
11.	Error detected in the report under review	10	25	15	30	35	115	3.48
		10	50	45	120	175	400	
		8.7	21.7	13.0	26.1	30.4	100.0	
12.	The nature of the error	10	25	20	25	35	115	3.43
		10	50	60	100	175	395	
		8.7	21.7	17.4	21.7	30.4	100.0	
13.	Significant impact of individual or cumulative errors	5	25	25	15	45	115	3.61
		4.3	21.7	21.7	13.0	39.1	100.0	
		5	50	75	60	225	415	
14.	Probability of unlawful error origin	5	30	30	5	45	115	3.48
		4.3	26.1	26.1	4.3	39.1	100.0	
		5	60	90	20	225	400	

Auditors participating in the questionnaire were asked to answer the question, "Which client-specific parameters do you consider important when determining the materiality indicator?" on a scale from 1 to 5 according to the level of significance. Fourteen parameters that are relevant for most audit clients when determining materiality were presented as possible response options (Table 4).

Table 4

A sequence of average values derived from the analysis of the client's response to which parameters do you primarily attach importance when determining the significance indicator (listed in ascending order of score based on Table 3)⁹

No	Customer Options	Weighted average significance level
1.	The auditor's relationship with shareholders	2.57
2.	Client's financial standing	3.22
	General state of the industry in which the enterprise operates	
3.	Work experience and qualifications of the auditor	3.26
	Customer Leadership Goals	

9 author's development

4.	Needs of Financial Information Users	3.30
5.	Purposes of the enterprise / shareholders (owners)	3.35
	Level of confidence in the internal control system	
6.	Scale (size) of the client enterprise	3.39
7.	The nature of the error	3.43
8.	Auditor's attitude towards risk	3.48
	Error detected in the report under review	
	Probability of unlawful error origin	
9.	Significant impact of individual or cumulative errors	3.61

The analysis of the auditor-respondents' answers showed that, when determining the materiality indicator, practicing auditors assigned 3.61 points to the importance of considering the significant impact of individual or aggregate client errors. This means that in more than 72% of cases, auditors make decisions based on the assessment of both individual and aggregate errors.

Furthermore, the auditor's risk attitude, the error identified in the audited financial statements, and the possible legal implications of an identified error each received 3.48 points. This indicates that auditors take all three factors into account in approximately 70% of cases (Table 4).

Among the analyzed parameters, the lowest score was assigned to the auditor's relationship with shareholders, which received 2.57 points on the 5-point scale. This shows that this factor is considered in approximately 50% of cases. In addition, the financial condition of the audited client and the general state of the industry in which the enterprise operates each received 3.22 points. This indicates that auditors consider both of these parameters in approximately 65% of cases.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis of the questionnaire responses, it can be concluded that the application of ISA 320 in audit practice within the Republic of Uzbekistan has reached a certain level of development. The finding that revenue is used as the primary benchmark for determining materiality in more than 80% of cases is generally consistent with international practice. At the same time, international studies indicate that profit before tax is also widely used as a benchmark. In the present study, this indicator ranked second in terms of weighted average value. The use of total assets as a benchmark was likewise found to be consistent with international auditing practice.

Users of financial statements are generally divided into internal and external users. While internal users have direct access to financial information, external users primarily rely on financial statements as a source of information. From this perspective, the reliability and credibility of financial statements are of paramount importance. Therefore, entities subject to statutory audits present their financial statements after they have been examined by independent auditors. In this process, the auditor's primary objective is to provide stakeholders with reasonable assurance that the financial statements have been prepared in accordance with the applicable reporting standards.

A reasonable level of assurance does not imply absolute certainty, as financial reporting and auditing are inherently subject to certain limitations associated with the client's internal characteristics and control environment. The acceptable threshold of such uncertainty is reflected through the concept of materiality. Consequently, in determining the materiality level, auditors should carefully evaluate the factors that may influence the identification and assessment of material misstatements. Previous studies have shown that factors such as the size of the audited entity, the effectiveness of the internal control system, the objectives of management and shareholders, the auditor's professional experience, industry knowledge, and the nature of the auditor-client relationship may influence the determination of materiality.

The hypotheses proposed in this study were evaluated on the basis of the empirical findings obtained.

First Hypothesis (H1): The hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between client firm size and the determined materiality level was not supported by the empirical results. The majority of auditor-respondents selected revenue, total assets, and profit before tax as the main benchmarks, indicating that firm size is an important consideration in determining materiality.

Second Hypothesis (H2): The hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between the degree of closeness to the client and the determined materiality level was not supported. The parameters "Auditor's relationship with shareholders" and "Enterprise/shareholder objectives" received scores of 2.57 and 3.35, respectively, suggesting that these factors are taken into account to a certain extent when determining materiality.

Third Hypothesis (H3): The hypothesis stating that the auditor's professional experience does not affect the materiality level was not supported. The average score of 3.26 indicates that professional experience is regarded as an important factor

in establishing materiality.

Fourth Hypothesis (H4): The hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between reliance on the internal control system and the determined materiality level was not supported. The score of 3.35 demonstrates that auditors consider the effectiveness of the client's internal control system when determining materiality.

Fifth Hypothesis (H5): The hypothesis stating that there is no relationship between the likelihood of an error having legal implications and the materiality level was not supported. The corresponding parameter received a score of 3.48, indicating that a substantial proportion of auditors consider the potential legal implications of identified errors when determining materiality.

In summary, the empirical findings suggest that all five examined factors have a meaningful influence on the determination of materiality in audit practice. Accordingly, the alternative hypotheses received empirical support, highlighting the multidimensional nature of materiality judgments and the importance of both quantitative and qualitative considerations in the audit process.

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